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SOYA O'SIMLIGINING O'SISH VA RIVOJLANISHI**Amonova Dildora Bahodirovna**

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada soya o'simligining biologik xususiyatlari, o'sish va rivojlanish bosqichlari to'g'risida ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Uchtalik barg, dukkak, urug'palla barg, gipokotil

Soya o'simligi taxminan 4500 yil oldin xitoyda uy sharoitida o'stirilgan. Soya o'simligi dukkakdoshlar (Fabaceae) oilasiga, Glycina hipsida maxsim-turiga mansub bir yillik o'tsimon o'simlik. Soya barglari murakkab, uch bargchali, toq patsimon, yon bargchali. Ildizi o'q idiz, tuproqqa 1,5- 2m kiradi. Gullari qiyshiq (zigamorf), mayda, to'pguli shingil, barg qo'ltig'ida joylashadi.

Soya o'sish va rivojlanishiga ko'ra, ertapishar vegetatsiya (o'sish) davri 90-100 kun, o'rtapishar 110-120 kun, kechpishar 130-140 kunli navlarga bo'linadi. O'sish davriga ko'ra vegetativ va reproduktiv fazalarga bo'linadi.

Vegetativ o'sish bosqichlari:

VE-unib chiqish, Bu bosqichda soya urug'i o'z vaznining taxminan 50% ga teng bo'lgan suvni singdirish orqali unib chiqish jarayonini boshlaydi. Shishgan urug'dan birinchi bo'lib radikal yoki birlamchi ildiz chiqadi va pastga qarab cho'ziladi. Ko'p o'tmay gipokotil (poya) tuproq yuzasiga qarab cho'zila boshlaydi va o'zi bilan cotiledonlari (qarama -qarshi joylashgan urug' barglarni) yuqoriga tortadi. Urug'palla barglar tuproq yuzasiga mahkam yopilgan va pastga egilgan holda paydo bo'ladi va ular yer yuzasiga chiqqach tezda to'g'rilanib ochiladi. Bu bosqich harorat, namlik, ekish chuqurligi va o'sish sharoitiga qarab, 7-14 kun o'tgach paydo bo'ladi. Kotiledonlar (urug'palla barglar) yosh o'simiklarning paydo bo'lishi va paydo bo'lgandan keyingi taxminan 7-10 kun davomida ozuqa moddalarga bo'lgan ehtiyojni ta'minlaydi.

VC- Boshlang'ich barglar (cotiledonlar); o'ralgan bittalik barg (yagona) barg hosil qilish bosqichi; Gipokotil paydo bo'lgandan so'ng, tezda kotiledonlar ochilib to'g'rilanadi va o'sishni to'xtatadi. Bu bosqichda epikotil (yosh barglar, poya va kotiledon tugunining tepasiga joylashgan o'sish nuqtasi) ochiladi. Birlamchi barglarning ochilishi va kengayishi kotiledon bosqichini boshlanishini anglatadi.. Bu vaqtda kotiledonlar o'z vaznining taxminan 70 foizini yo'qotadi. Agar shu davrda kotiledonlar yo'qolsa yoki zararlansa, ko'chatlar bo'yi o'sishdan to'xtaydi va hosildorlik 8-9 foizga kamayishi mumkin.

Unib chiqish bosqichidan 2-3 kun o'tgach bir-biriga simmetrik joylashgan bir juft oddiy tuxumsimon barglar paydo bo'ladi. Bitta barg to'la shakllanishi uchun 10-12 kun sarf bo'ladi.

V1 – birinchi o'ralgan uchtalik barglar. Bu bosqich urug'lar unib chiqqandan 7-10 kundan keyin hosil bo'ladi. Bu davrda haqiqiy barglar, yon kurtaklar.

V2 – ikkinchi o'ralgan uch talik barglar. Bu davr birinchi uch talik barglar hosil bo'lgandan 2-3 kun o'tgach hosil bo'ladi

V3- uchinchi o'ralgan uch bargli barglar ochiladi, bu bosqichda azot fiksatsiyasi boshlanishi mumkin.

V4- bu davrda ildiz sistemasi jadal rivojlanadi, barglarda organik moddalar to'plana boshlaydi.

V5- beshinchi uch barglar bosqichi; bu davrda g'unchalash boshlanadi va birinchi gullar shakllanadi.

Rn- n uch talik barglarning hosil bo'lishi

Reproduktiv bosqichlar. (gullashdan yetuklik bosqichigacha o'z ichiga oladi)

R1-Gullashning boshlanishi; Maysalar unib chiqqandan keyin o'sish sharoitiga va naviga qarab 28-33 kunlarida, takroriy ekin sifatida ekilganda esa, 17-23 kun o'tgach gullashni boshlaydi. Har qanday tugunda kamida bitta gul ochilganda sodir bo'ladi. Bu bosqichda o'simlik jadal o'sishni boshlaydi, o'simlik bo'yi (38-46 sm) ga yetadi. Bu fazada o'simlik bo'yigagina o'sib qolmasdan ildizlarning o'sishi ham jadallashadi. Yon ildizlarning hosil bo'lishi hamda ularda tuganaklar shakllana boshlaydi. Bu bosqichda o'simlik asosiy poyasida 8-16ta barg bo'ladi.

R2-To'liq gullash; ikkita yuqori tugunlardan birida ochiq gul bo'lganda sodir bo'ladi va ikkita yuqori tugunning kamida bittasida to'liq rivojlangan barg bo'ladi. Bu bosqichda o'simlik (43-56 sm gacha) balandlikda bo'ladi. To'liq gullash bosqichida ildiz sistemasi yaxshi rivojlangan bo'ladi. Gullash davri soya naviga qarab 30-35 kun davom etadi.

R3- Dukkak rivojlanishining boshlanishi; dukkaklash bosqichi dastlabki gullar ochilganidan 11-14 kun o'tgach kuzatiladi. Bu bosichda o'simlik bo'yi (58-81 sm) yetadi [2]

R4- To'liq dukkak (71-100sm),

R5- Boshlang'ich urug'lik; boshlang'ich urug'lar asosiy poyadagi 4ta yuqori tugunning 1tasida 3mm bo'lganda boshlanadi.

R6- To'liq urug'lik- yashil urug'lar po'st hajmini to'ldirganda.

R7 -pishishning boshlanishi asosiy poyadagi 1 dona dukkakning pishgan rangga erishganda sodir bo'ladi, bu davrda dukkaklarda organik birikmalarning to'planishi jadallashadi. O'simlik o'sishdan to'xtaydi. Ildiz, poya, barg og'irligi kamayadi

R8- to'liq yetuklik dukkaklarning 95 foizi pishgan rangga erishganda sodir bo'ladi. Bu bosqichi boshqa fazalar orasida eng qisqasi bo'lib 11-15 kun davom etadi. Soya o'simligi dukkaklari pishib yetilishi bilan barglari sarg'ayib, birin-

ketin tabiiy to'kalishni boshlaydi. Soya ekini respublikamizda keng tarqalmagan, doimo ekib kelinmagan, shuning uchun soya ekilgan maydonlarda maxsus nitragin yoki rizotorfin qo'llanganda biologik simbioz ro'y beradi. Soya urug'lari nitragin shtammlari bilan ishlov berib ekilganda vegetativ va generativ organlar shakllanishi va hosildorlik yaxshilanadi. Urug'larni ekishdan oldin ishlov berishda foydalanuvchi barcha turdagi ishlov berish uslublaridan foydalanilgan sharoitda, urug'larning ekishga oid sifat darajasi (ya'ni, o'sish energiyasi, unuvchanlik) yaxshilanishi, o'simliklarning o'sish-rivojlanishi tezlashishi qayd qilinadi, o'z navbatida o'simliklarning tashqi muhitning noqulay ta'sirga ega omillariga nisbatan chidamlilik darajasi ortadi va yakuniy holatda hosildorlik qiymatining 5-20 % gacha ortishiga erishiladi.[3,4]

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ЛЕКСИК ТАКРОРНИНГ БАЪЗИ ЖИХАТЛАРИ ХУСУСИДА

Маҳмудова Лобар Исмоилжоновна

Андижон вилояти Булоқбоши тумани ХТБ га қарашли 17-умумий ўрта таълим мактаби ўқитувчиси

Анотация: Ушбу мақолада лексик такрор гаплар ўртасидаги синтактик алоқалар ва нутқда уларнинг структуравий боғланиши ифода воситаси бўлиб хизмат қилиши хусусида сўз боради.

Abstract: This article discusses the syntactic relationships between lexical repetitions and their structural relationships in speech as a means of expression.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются синтаксические связи между лексическими повторениями и их структурные связи в речи как средство выражения.

Маълумки, турли тизимли тилларда сўзлар такрори воситасида рўёбга чиқадиган боғланиш лексик такрор орқали ифодаланган занжир боғланиш деб аталади. Такрорланувчи сўзларнинг синтактик вазифасига кўра "эга - эга", "эга - тўлдирувчи", "тўлдирувчи - эга" ва бошқа турдаги боғланиш кўринишлари қайд этилади. [1.15]

Лексик такрор ўзича маъно касб этмайди. У фақатгина гапларнинг ички структуравий моделлар (тўлдирувчи - эга ва ҳк.) бўйича рўёбга чиқувчи синтактик алоқани кўрсатиб беради.

Лексик такрор фақатгина ушбу алоқани очиб беради, аммо шуни таъкидлаш жоиз-ки, лексик такрор гарчи муҳим бўлса-да, мустақил гаплар ўртасидаги синтактик боғланишнинг ягона воситаси эмас. Гапдаги сўзлар боғланишида ҳам биз маълум грамматик структуралардангина (мавхум структуравий схема) фойдаланишимиз мумкин, шунингдек, тугал гаплар боғланишида ҳам бизнинг "эркинлигимиз" анча нисбий. Ёндош гаплардаги маълум гап бўлаги такрорида ўз ифодасини топган тугал гаплар боғланишининг маълум структуравий типлари ҳам мавжуд. [3.22]

Тугал гапларнинг бундай узвий алоқаси монологик нутқдан ҳам жой олган. Нутқ оқимидаги гаплар ўзаро узвий боғланган ва одатда олдинги гап кейинги гап структурасини боғлиқ ҳолга келтиради.

Шундай қилиб, конматндаги ёндош гаплар таркибидаги маълум сўз ёки сўзлар гуруҳи такрори нафақат лексик хусусият касб этади, улар, шунингдек, энг аввало синтактик характерга эга: бу - гаплар ўртасидаги синтактик боғланишнинг ўзига хос кўрсаткичи ҳисобланади. Уйғун нутқ оқимида такрор қатъий боғланган. Кейинги гапда ҳар қандай олдинги

гапдан эркин саралаб олинган сўз эмас, балки маъно жиҳатидан ажратилдиган, мантиқий урғу олувчи сўз такрорланади.

Биринчи гапда структура жиҳатидан (мантиқий, оҳанг жиҳатидан ҳам) маълум бир сўз ажратилади-ки, ушбу сўзда кейинчалик ривожланишга мойил фикр объективлаштирилгандек туюлади. [2.43]

Кейинчалик ушбу сўз тўла ёки қисман такрорланади. Худди шундай ҳолат кейинчалик ҳам фикр ривожига яқинлашади давом этади.

Мустақил гаплар боғланишида улардаги такрорланаётган сўз, юқорида айтиб ўтилганидек, гапларда бир хил бўлмаган синтактик ролни бажаради. Масалан, биринчиси гапда у тўлдирувчи, иккинчисидан эса эга бўлиб келиши мумкин. Ёндош гаплардаги монандлашган лексик бўлақлар муносабати улар ўртасидаги грамматик (синтактик) алоқани вужудга келтиради-ки, бу нарса лексик такрорда энг яққол кўзга ташланади.

Лексик такрор гаплар ўртасидаги синтактик алоқанинг аниқ, лекин ягона бўлмаган кўрсаткичи, нутқда уларнинг структуравий боғланиши ифода воситаси бўлиб хизмат қилади. Лексик такрордан ташқари занжир боғланишнинг ифода воситалари сифатида бирикувчи гапларнинг боғланувчи бўлақларида синонимик сўзлар қўлланиши мумкин, такрорланувчи сўз ва бошқалар ўрнига турли олмошларни ишлатиш кузатилади. Масалан, У Миши была дворняжка. Собаку звали Пальмой. Аммо занжир боғланиш ифода воситаларининг хилма-хиллигидан қатъий назар унинг моҳияти ўзгармайди, такрор ҳам, синонимик лексика ҳам, олмошлар ҳам уйғун нутқ тугал гаплари ўртасидаги барқарор синтактик муносабатларни нутқда намоён этади. [4.25]

Шундай қилиб, занжир боғланишда икки ўзаро узвий боғланган томонни фарқлаш лозим: бирикаётган гапларнинг барқарор боғланувчи бўлақларида ўз ифодасини топган ички, структуравий (тўлдирувчи - эга, эга - эга, тўлдирувчи - тўлдирувчи ва ҳк.) ва ифода воситаларини тавсиф этувчи ташқи боғланиш, нутқда ушбу синтактик муносабатларнинг намоён бўлиши (лексик такрор, синонимик лексика, олмошлар). Шунга биноан занжир боғланишни гапларнинг структуравий боғланишига кўра таснифлаш мумкин, яъни ўзига хос моделларни, жуфтликларни (тўлдирувчи - эга ва ҳк.) шакллантирган ҳолда гапларнинг қайси бўлақлари ўзаро боғланишига, ифода воситаларига, ушбу моделларнинг "тўлдирилиши"га кўра таснифлаш мақсадга мувофиқдир. Шунга асосланган ҳолда ўз ифодасини лексик такрорда, кетма-кет синонимик ва олмошли боғланишда топган занжир боғланишни ажратамиз. Ушбу боғланишларнинг структуравий кўринишлари эса уларнинг лексик

либосларидан қатъий назар ҳамма жойда бир хил, яъни ифода воситасига кўра занжир боғланишнинг юқорида кўрсатиб ўтилган ҳар бир кўриниши ичида бир хил синтактик воситаларни фарқлашимиз мумкин - тўлдирувчи - эга, эга - эга ва ҳоказо. Уларда занжир боғланишнинг синтактик моҳияти, унинг асосий маъноси ўз ифодасини топади. [2. 59]

Занжир боғланиш - ҳукмлар боғланиши хусусиятини акс эттирувчи ва тугал синтактик бирлик сифатида намоён бўлувчи гап табиатига монанд келувчи мустақил гапларнинг бирикув воситаларидан биридир. Занжир боғланиш гапларнинг структуравий кетма-кетлигида намоён бўлади.

Фикрнинг бир гапдан иккинчиси томон мунтазам ҳаракати, ривожидан олдинги гапда урғу олган сўзнинг (гап бўлагининг) такрорланиб келишида ва унинг кейинги гапда ифодаланишида рўёбга чиқади. Ҳар қандай тугал гаплар бирикувининг фикр изчил ҳаракатида такрорсиз, олдинги гап бўлагининг ривожисиз амалга ошуви мумкин эмас.

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HOW TO OPEN A PRESCHOOL ORGANIZATION ON THE BASIS OF A PRIVATE PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP: STEP-BY-STEP INSTRUCTIONS**Olimovna Dilnoza Nurmatova****Head of Preschool Education Department of Buvayda district, Chairman of Ozlidep Community Council.**

These tips are aimed at individuals who want to open a preschool organization on the basis of their public-private partnership. These include: Family Non-Governmental Preschool Education Organization, SPCO-operation, and private preschools. The Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 595 of July 30, 2018 and the Resolution No. 944 of November 11, 2018 and the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-5144 of June 10, 2021 can be used on this topic. Citizens wishing to work in this field do not hesitate to provide advice and assistance to entrepreneurs when applying to the specialists of the public-private partnership departments of the Ministry of Preschool Education, public-private partnership departments in the provinces and districts.

The idea of opening a public-private partnership preschool organization seems simple and straightforward (in this case, you can own up to 25 or 50 in FNGPEO vacant rooms of your private yard with an area of not less than 5 sots, 50 to 300 in non-residential private buildings with an area of not less than 20

sots. you will have the opportunity to open a pre-school or private non-governmental preschool. There is also no need to be upset if you don't have personal property. To do this, it is possible to open a non-governmental preschool organization by concluding a lease agreement with the property owner or government agencies. Vacancies of government organizations can also be purchased through auctions. Entrepreneurs who decide to open a non-governmental preschool organization should first make the building in a child-friendly form, fill it with equipment and make it interesting and attractive. In this case, the entrepreneur will be able to receive and prepare preferential loans from the state with the provision of personal funds or a design estimate for the kindergarten.

The permission of the Education Inspectorate is sufficient to open a private preschool. It is necessary to conclude an agreement with the Ministry of Preschool Education to open a preschool organization on the basis of public-private partnership. The following documents must be submitted for the transaction.

1. An application shall be addressed to the Minister of Preschool Education.
2. Application addressed to the heads of local territorial departments of the Ministry of Preschool Education.

3. Cadastral documents of the apartment, if the citizen does not have personal property (Lease agreement)
4. Conclusion from CEO and JSB
5. Conclusion from fire safety
6. Bank account.
7. Photos from 6 different views of the apartment

Once the documents are ready, an agreement is made with the Ministry of Preschool Education and the entrepreneur is issued a certificate to start operations. The 25-seat FNGPEO has two staff members: a tutor and an assistant tutor, who are paid a monthly salary by the state. Subsidies are allocated for food for each child. An entrepreneur who opens a 50-seat FNGPEO will be able to create 4 jobs. What about when you open a DXS? Now you can be a leader like public kindergartens and get paid. In this, too, our state will help you and pay the salaries of your educators, nurses and other staff. In addition, the state provides subsidies for food for each foster child. Only the entrepreneur is required to cover children aged 3-7 and receive 70% of the foster children on a preferential basis and use the DHS building for 30 years only for kindergarten.

There is also an opportunity to open a private non-governmental preschool education organization at the request of the entrepreneur. In this case, the entrepreneur can admit children from 6 months to 7 years of age in preschool educational institutions, where the age of pupils is not limited, and the amount of child benefits can be determined by the entrepreneur at his discretion. For a private non-governmental preschool organization, the state provides tax breaks. But no money is allocated for staff and students.

If you are interested in working with children, if you want to invest in the primary level of education, if you want the next generation to be more educated, you should not waste time. It is necessary to move forward with courage and open a non-governmental preschool organization.

To my familiar entrepreneurs: "Where do you start if you want to start your own public-private preschool?" they replied almost in unison: "We would look for a suitable room, buy the necessary equipment." Yes we really need buildings, equipment and some start with that. But the most important thing is education in our field, it is necessary to find qualified and sufficiently educated teachers and to open a kindergarten in consultation with them.

First of all, pupils need education, rich in vitamins, delicious food and modern conditions. All these tips will help you to open a non-preschool organization that meets the requirements of today, at a time when competition is strong.

**THE IMPORTANCE OF DIFFERENT GAMES IN EDUCATION OF
HYPERACTIVE CHILDREN OF PRESCHOOL AGE****Istamova Dilnoza Norboyevna****Termez State University****5A111801 Theory of education and upbringing****Preschool education specialty****2-year master's degree**

Annotation: The main function of emotion in a person is to ensure that these people can understand each other unconditionally, engage in joint activities and communication. In order to carry out this process more successfully, a person must be able to control his emotional state, his emotions by his own willpower.

Keywords: Hyperactive children, categorical words, "Sun and rain", "You were in a hurry - you laughed", "Where did they play?" "Find what I'm playing", methods of psychological correction

INTRODUCTION

Today, every citizen of our country is aware of the unprecedented changes in the field of preschool education. It is no exaggeration to say that the state has not received so much systematic and complementary attention and practical assistance to the pre-school education system, which is the basis of education.

The issue of solving the problems in the field and ensuring the full education of children aged 3 to 7 years was put forward by the President as an urgent task. The reason is that instead of fulfilling the role of a kindergarten, the kindergarten has become a child-care facility for parents while at work, low coverage, repair of buildings, use for other purposes, incomplete methodological support, teachers solving complex problems such as social protection and low wages was an urgent issue. Over the past 20 years, the number of state-run preschools has dropped by 45 percent, with only 818,000 of the 2.45 million children enrolled in kindergartens. The poor condition of the infrastructure and material and technical base of pre-school education institutions did not allow to ensure full coverage of children with pre-school education.

Shortcomings, such as delays in the development of the sector, delays in the opening of non-governmental kindergartens, and incomplete construction of local kindergartens, have led to a number of shortcomings. The study showed that the current system of preschool education management did not allow to identify and address existing problems in a timely manner, as well as to develop and implement innovative solutions for further development of the sector ...

The meeting on August 16, 2017 was a meeting that will go down in the history of the preschool education system. On the same day, the President of our country spoke about strengthening the national gene pool of the state and

identified many areas for the development of the first stage of education.

Hyperactive children do not always adequately understand parental affection, so they need unconditional parental love and trust in others.

What advice can be given to the parents of a hyperactive child and thus help in their upbringing?

The first group of recommendations applies to the external side of adult behavior that is close to the child.

- Efforts should be made to reverse the effects of violence resulting from the child's behavior. Encourage children emotionally in all attempts at constructive and positive behavior, no matter how insignificant. Develop an interest in the child to know and understand more.

- Avoid categorical words and phrases, harsh assessments, reprimands, threats that provoke and provoke conflict in the family. Try to say less "no", "no", "don't stop" - it's better to try to change the baby's attention and do it with a joke if possible.

- Monitor your speech, try to speak in a calm voice. Anger is less controlled. Express your dissatisfaction, do not manipulate the child's feelings and do not insult him.

The recommendations of the second group relate to the regulation of the family environment and the environment.

- If possible, try to set aside room or part of the room for the child for lessons, games, solitude (i.e., his or her own "area"). It is advisable to avoid bright colors and complex compositions in the design. There should be no distractions on the table and in the immediate vicinity of the child. The hyperactive child himself cannot be sure that nothing external will distract him.

- Organizing the whole life should have a calming effect on the child. To do this, create a daily routine that shows you to be flexible and resilient at the same time.

- Determine the technical conditions for the child and keep their operation under constant supervision and control, but not too strict. Often his efforts are celebrated and praised, although the results are not very good.

The recommendations of the third group focus on the child's active interaction with close adults, the development of the ability of both adults and children to feel each other, emotional rapprochement.

And the most important activity for children here is absolutely unchanging - play, because it is close and understandable to the child. The use of emotional influences in the form of voices, facial expressions, gestures, and adults' attitudes toward their own actions and the child's actions is a great pleasure for both

participants.

Hyperactivity is generally understood to be an excessive disturbance of physical and mental activity in children, rather than inhibiting excitement. Doctors believe that hyperactivity is the result of very little brain damage that has not been detected by diagnostic tests. From a scientific point of view, we are dealing with minimal brain dysfunction.

What are the causes of hyperactivity?

The causes of this syndrome are not yet fully understood. But many experts point out the following among the reasons.

- pregnancy toxicosis,
- congenital pathology,
- infection and intoxication in the first years of life of the baby,
- genetic factors
- chronic parental alcoholism.

METHOD

"Sun and rain" game

Educator, we are going on a trip with you now. The weather is nice, the sun is shining. I play the circle. You walk around picking flowers in a circle. If it starts to rain, I start clicking the circle. And you have to run to your houses when you hear the knock of the circle.

"What is the ball screaming" game

Shows toys of cows, puppies, cats, sheep, etc. one by one and imitates their voice. The child is asked to open the door of another room or imitate the sound of an animal in a small house. The other children find out which animal's voice it is.

The fairy tale "You hurried - you laughed"

The frog jumped in front of the bear's house. Standing under the window, he said, "Occasionally we came to visit you," and then the mouse said, "Pi-pi-pi, your sum is very tasty." At that time, the chicken said, "Go-ko-ko, you are scattered and told to go and undress." After the chicken, a goose came. Then the bear called his head out of the window and said, "Rrrrrr." When the animals heard this, they ran away in fear. And the bear wants to say that. "" R-r-r "I'm so glad the guests are welcome. The participants of the fairy tale should be shown on the Flonelograph while telling.

"Where did they play?" game

The children sit in a circle. The educator chooses a game starter. The starter is in the middle. The beginner closed his eyes at the educator's signal. One of the children rings the bell. Without opening his eyes, the ringer points to the direction of the incoming call.

The educator says "it's done" and the child opens his eyes. The child who rang the bell picks up the bell and shows it. If the child goes astray, he will return again. Then another child will be the starter.

"Whose bird flies far" game

Ribbons, birds, butterflies are fixed, hung and blown out of thin paper.

"Find what I'm playing" game

The educator introduces the child to musical toys. He then hides the toys behind a curtain. Behind the scenes, he plays a musical toy and asks the children which musical toy he played. Whoever finds it right, this boy will play a musical toy behind the curtain. 4 different musical toys should be taken in one lesson.

"High-low" game

The barking of small and large dogs is practiced.

"Who is he?" game

In another room, the educator prepares masks for dogs, cats, geese, chickens and goats. A masked boy knocks on the door. The children asked, "Who is he?" he says. A child wearing a dog mask responds with a "wow-wow-wow".

CONCLUSION

A child's lagging behind in parenting and learning is the result of a child's failure to master mental functions. For example, a child's clothing sequence may be impaired not because of poor memory, but because he or she has not acquired the skills needed to perform the process. Along with ways to psychoregulate this mental problem, the child may be presented with pictures depicting the correct sequence of clothing. L.S. Vygotsky argues that the social environment is of paramount importance for children with disabilities. He also likens the development of children with disabilities to a bad root system. "Its thin roots do not match the layers and shape of the nutrient soil. They do not reach the nutrient layers of the soil on their own and enter the dry and toxic layer. It could have flourished under the right conditions, but under normal conditions it did not reach the peak of development and withered," he said. Therefore, it is expedient to develop the education system taking into account the specifics of each nation and ethnic group, national traditions, customs, goals of the state and the characteristics of the mental and physical development of students. In children with disabilities, if the adults help the child as much as possible without resisting his or her opinion and independence, the difficulties in the process of forming his or her personality will disappear on their own. Stubbornness, stubbornness, and disobedience in a child with a disability are caused by the over-indulgence of these adults. Psychologist LM Krijanovskaya describes in detail the ways of educating children with disabilities through the methods of psychological

correction in the system of inclusive education. In his opinion, the effectiveness of educational work in the system of inclusive education should be closely linked with the cooperation of school psychologists, teachers, educators and parents in achieving good results.

In this regard, teachers can be recommended:

1. Organize work with a hyperactive child individually, with the main focus on the child's distraction.
2. To ignore as much as possible the irritating behavior of a child with attention deficit disorder and to encourage his good behavior.

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**TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE FORMATION OF CREATIVE ABILITIES IN
FUTURE TEACHERS****Babakeldiyeva Aziza Abdusamatovna****Termez State University****Faculty of Social Sciences****Department of Preschool Education Methods****Teacher**

Annotation: In this article, future educators will be introduced to the principles of the general principles of creative pedagogy, and methods, techniques, tools and technologies that develop the qualities of creativity. views on the development of creative approach skills to the organization.

Keywords: creative person, "creative pedagogy", creative thinking, intellectual idea, creativity.

INTRODUCTION

It is not so long ago that the concept of "creative pedagogy" began to be used in modern pedagogy. However, the need for innovative and creative approaches to the teaching process has led to the formation of "Creative Pedagogy" as an independent subject among a range of pedagogical disciplines. The basis of this subject is the methodological ideas of such disciplines as the history of pedagogy, general and professional pedagogy and psychology, methods of teaching special subjects, educational technology and professional ethics. The general principles of the subject of "creative pedagogy" serve to create the necessary conditions for the professional development of professionals, including future professionals. The professional development of a person as a specialist is, in essence, a process. Professional maturity is an important period of human ontogeny, which begins with the development of professional ideas, the development of ideas (14-17 years) and the end of professional activity (55-60 years).

The formation and development of a creative person depends on the interaction of changes in his inner and outer world, socio-economic conditions and the human ontogeny - the content of activities that require continuity, succession from birth to the end of life. As you know, professional experience is an integration of knowledge, skills and abilities. However, the acquisition of professional skills is not only the integration of practical skills and abilities, the development of methods and tools for effective organization of activities as a specialist, but also awareness of the methodology of professional creativity, development of creative thinking and creativity. requires adequate mastery of personal qualities of character. The formation of a creative person can be defined as the development of an individual in the creation of creative activities and creative products in a mutually compatible way. The speed and scope of this

process depends on biological and social factors, individual activity and creative qualities, as well as existing conditions, vital and professionally conditioned events.

In today's world, it is important for educators to be creative. In recent years, the education system of leading foreign countries has paid special attention to the formation of creative qualities in students. This was followed by Bronson, Merriyman (2010), Ken Robinson (2007), Fisher, Frey (2008), Begetto, Kaufman (2013), Ali (2011), Treffinger (2008), and b. Many studies have been conducted by Only Ken Robinson's 2007 "Is School Destroying Creativity?" The video has been viewed 5 million times on YouTube. In addition, teachers are serious about learning the basics of creativity (Begetto, Kaufman, 2013). Literature on the formation and development of creative approach skills, pedagogical skills in teachers is published, non-traditional lessons based on videos prepared by the Department of Education are organized (Ali, 2011; Department of Education, 2013).

Despite significant practical work, many teachers still do not have the experience of how to effectively form the qualities of creativity in themselves and in students. For this purpose, a curriculum will be developed, new textbooks will be created, which will help both students and teachers to grow professionally. However, by the end of the academic year, there is no high level of positive results in the study of subjects by students in higher education institutions. He has lost interest in learning. As a result, teachers are still enjoying themselves he is not eager to pursue a career.

Although new measures have been taken by the education authorities to change the activities of teachers who are reluctant to teach such students, the situation has worsened. remains unchanged. What is the reason for this? Perhaps it is not interesting for the students to think about the lessons planned in advance, but maybe the fact that the content of the education is in a certain pattern does not give any incentive to the students. Rejection of pre-planning of lessons, formation and development of critical, creative thinking in students, creative thinking, forcing them to come up with new ideas, changing attitudes to education, encouraging them to succeed 'will be a key factor in the battalion.

METHOD

What is lacking in the classroom is creativity. To fully understand the general nature of the process of developing creative qualities in a person, it is first necessary to understand the meaning of the concept of "creativity". According to Ken Robinson, "creativity is a set of original ideas that have their own value" (Azzam, 2009). Gardner explains the concept in his research: "Creativity is a

practical action performed by an individual, which must reflect a certain innovation and have a certain practical value." In Emebayl's (1989) approach, creativity means "having a high level of extraordinary skills in addition to the thorough knowledge acquired in a particular field." Many studies differ on the relationship between intelligence and creativity. While one group of researchers argues that there is no correlation between them, the second group argues that the level of creativity and intelligence are interrelated (Kim, 2005). The concept of "creativity" reflects cultural diversity. For Westerners, creativity is a novelty in general. They focus on non-traditionalism, curiosity, imagination, a sense of humor, and freedom based on creativity (Myordok, Ganim, 1993; Sternberg, 1985). Orientals, on the other hand, see creativity as a process of rebirth of goodness (Hui, Sternberg, 2002; Rudovich, Hui, 1997; Rudovich, Yue, 2000). Although Western and Eastern views on creativity are different, both cultures value and possess this quality (Kaufman, Lan, 2012).

Many educators believe that they do not have the ability to be creative. There are two reasons for this: first, most teachers do not adequately explain what the concept of "creativity" actually means; second, they are unaware of what qualities are directly reflected in creativity. It is important to note that each person is by nature creative. So how can teachers show that they are creative? Patti Drapeau advises: "Even if you think you are not creative, I suggest you start organizing lessons to develop creative thinking right now. It's not about whether you're creative or not, it's about being creative and trying new ideas." 5 According to Patti Drapeau, creative thinking is, first and foremost, comprehensive thinking on a particular issue. Comprehensive thinking requires students to rely on a wide range of ideas in their assignments, tasks, and responsibilities. In contrast, one-sided thinking is based on a single correct idea. There is no denying the one-sided and multi-faceted approach to the issue in observation. Consequently, one-sided and all-round thinking is equally important in shaping creativity. In YA, the task is to solve the problem, the student looks for several solutions (multi-faceted thinking), and then stops at the only correct solution that guarantees the most optimal result (one-sided thinking). Based on the above, the concept of "creativity" can be interpreted as follows:

Creativity (Latin, "create" - to create, "creative" - creator, creator) - the creative ability of an individual, which characterizes the readiness to produce new ideas and is part of the talent as an independent factor.

A person's creativity is reflected in his thinking, communication, emotions, and certain activities. Creativity describes a person as a whole or its specific characteristics. Creativity is also reflected in an important factor of talent. In

addition, creativity determines the sharpness of the mind, "ensuring the active involvement of students in the educational process." In foreign countries, teachers, as well as experts in all fields, determine the degree and level of creativity. To do this, they are tested by E.P. Torrens, based in 1987, to determine if a person has creative thinking. This test allows you to assess a person's creativity and its level on such criteria as activity in the organization of creative activity, quick thinking, originality and sophistication. The answers to the student's suggested questions should meet these four criteria. According to E.P. Torrens, the concept of "creativity" is based on the following.

- put forward a problem or scientific hypotheses;
 - check and change the hypothesis;
 - identify the problem based on the formation of the decision;
 - knowledge and practical actions in finding a solution to the problem
- sensitivity to reciprocity

Creative thinking can be clearly reflected in every social area. The creativity of a teacher is reflected in his / her creative approach to the organization of professional activity. In recent years, this situation has been characterized by the concept of "pedagogical creativity".

CONCLUSION

Based on the above, it can be concluded that the systematic study of pedagogical needs, interests, areas of special importance of students, while identifying effective ways to overcome the countersuggestive, thesaurus and interaction barriers encountered in the organization of their creative activities should. The organization of the teaching process based on ideas, concepts and best pedagogical practices that serve the creative interests and needs of students also serves to form a meaningful and active approach to the development of creativity. Based on the development of students' creative skills, it is necessary to pay special attention to the development of their specialized pedagogical competence, including the widespread use of modern information and communication technologies, innovative strategies, interactive teaching methods and technologies. Experts note that the development of creatively oriented educational programs to ensure the effectiveness of the reproductive, creative-research and innovative stages of development of creative abilities of students in higher education institutions and the development of students' creative skills and abilities. should be evaluated. Improving curricula and technologies aimed at the continuous development of creative competencies of teachers in higher education, as well as the creation of modern information and methodological

support to develop the creative abilities of students will increase the effectiveness of the process.

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**IMPROVING THE PSYCHOLOGICAL LITERACY OF PARENTS IN THE
QUALITY PREPARATION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN FOR SCHOOL
EDUCATION****Sheraliyeva Munavvar Abdullayevna****Termez State University****Faculty of Social Sciences****Department of Preschool Education Methods****teacher**

Annotation: The article theoretically and practically describes the importance of pedagogical and psychological literacy of parents in preparing children for school education.

Keywords: pedagogical and psychological literacy, school preparation, family education, kindergarten age, school education, parents, state curriculum, primary and preschool age, state requirements for development

INTRODUCTION.

Approval of the "Concept of development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" became a promising program for the development of the sector. One of the problems is that a number of systemic problems and shortcomings hinder the successful implementation of public policy in the field of preschool education, including insufficient knowledge of parents about the positive aspects and benefits of preschool education in the formation of the child's personality. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 29, 2016 No PP-2707 "On measures to further improve the system of preschool education in 2017-2021", the priorities of the Action Strategy for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan reveal the essence of reforms in preschool education. At the meeting chaired by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev on August 16, 2017, important tasks were set to radically reform the system of preschool education, to fully cover children in these institutions. As a result of the analysis, in a short period of time three major documents - the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 9, 2017 No PP-3261 "On measures to radically improve the system of preschool education", September 30, 2017 "On measures to radically improve the management of preschool education" Decree No. PF-5198 and Resolution No. PQ-3305 of September 30, 2017 "On the organization of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan"

Raising a child is a difficult and complex task that requires from all members of the family not only the right attitude towards children, but also a high sense of responsibility for their fate. Combining all aspects of family upbringing, including spiritual, moral, intellectual, aesthetic, physical and labor education, gives good

results. Parents are interested in preparing preschool children for school. This is understandable, because academic work requires hard work, effort, perseverance, the ability to achieve results. A preschooler is prepared for this new type of work not only during the training process, but also during the performance of any labor tasks. The skillful combination of collective and individual forms of work with parents, the achievement of pedagogical and psychological literacy among the general population and the effectiveness of educational and advocacy work. By creating a single learning environment, it is possible to achieve quality preparation of a child for school education. Parents are also concerned about preparing their preschool child for school. Questions arise as to what kind of student the child will be, whether he will be able to adapt to school without difficulty, and whether he will be able to do his homework. Most of our parents are having a hard time solving this problem. It has been found that most families are unaware of the fact that there are manuals designed to prepare children for school education in the family, published for parents. Parents face great challenges in using special guides distributed to families through schools. Now the level of readiness for school is not only a task of reading and learning, but also the social and emotional development of the child, the approach to learning, the development of physical and motor skills. Education is no longer just a child's job, but also a family that can help the child develop so that he or she is ready. So, it is important for parents to have the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities to prepare their child for school education in the family. Observations show that to date, the content of kindergarten teachers' work with parents has changed radically. As a result, the attitude of parents to kindergarten is also changing for the better. It is especially interesting to gradually acquaint parents with the requirements of the state. Some parents are asking educators for advice on what to do at home so that their child has a high level of development in this or that area. This is definitely a happy situation

METHOD

A child's readiness for school is determined by his physical and mental development, health, mental and personal development, that is, the whole set of factors is important. L. I. Bojovich introduced the concept of "school maturity" in psychology, which determines the level of morphological, functional and mental development of the child, according to which systemic learning requirements do not harm the child's health without excessive, as well as do not lead to school incompatibility. Low-level functional training is a lack of school, that is, the degree of maturity of certain structures in the brain, the incompatibility of neuro-mental functions with the tasks of teaching in school may be psychological reasons. Lack

of schooling is manifested in the low level of development of fine motor skills, "eye-hand" direction, imitation of the pattern of activity, behavior and other functions. At a young school age, non-compliance with school requirements is manifested in difficulties in meeting the requirements, low mastery, and various forms of indiscipline. Insufficient development of a free environment is a special reason for not adapting to school (first of all, inability to hear and follow the instructions of adults, inability to act in accordance with the rules, lack of free attention and free memory). A similar deficiency is caused by many difficulties in reading, indiscipline, and inability to work independently in the classroom and at home. Lack of formation of preschool types of thinking in young school-age students, phonetic hearing, insufficient development of speech, as well as incomprehensibility of the teacher's words may be the reasons for inability to adapt to school.

Determining a child's readiness to learn involves assessing the following key factors:

1. psychophysiological;

2. educational activity and its components:

- formation of the sensorimotor field;
- formation of cognitive processes;
- Presence of cognitive motivation.

3. formation of a system of self-management;

4. as a requirement and ability to establish social interactions with both peers and adults;

5. socialization, conformity and acceptance of the child's personal abilities to the requirements of society.

When it comes to mental readiness for school, psychophysiological readiness comes first. We are talking about the child's health. Anemia, hypo or hyperactivity, organic brain dysfunction, chronic insomnia, somatic diseases, etc. interfere with successful training and education. Because such a child is not able to physically perform school tasks.

As for learning activities, we are talking about the development of the sensomotor field, ie the fine work of the hand (motor skills), coordination of visual movements (eye - hand). Although the child observes the teacher's activities on the board, he or she should be able to repeat them in his or her notebook as he or she completes the tasks in the textbook. This function (eye-hand) is the basis for independent work with the textbook. Cognitive processes: processes that provide cognitive activity such as feeling, perception, attention, memory, thinking must be formed. Cognitive motivation consists in the formation of an interest in reading

and the desire to be a student. Reading motivation is formed when there is cognitive activity, but the above factors must be observed and the conditions must be created by the adult for the student to succeed.

The formation of a system of self-management consists not only in understanding the model and accepting the learning task, but also in being able to independently set, plan and implement activities that meet the requirements of the social environment surrounding the child.

The social factor implies the ability to establish relationships with both peers and adults. Because school is primarily a new social environment, a child's success as a student and a member of society depends on his or her ability to adapt to school conditions and interact with others. Adaptation means not only the mechanisms of adaptation to the situation, but also the ability of the child to establish independent relationships.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS.

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations were developed:

- organization of short-term training seminars, thematic seminars-trainings, round tables for parents in mahallas and schools in districts;

- Preparation of handouts for families, the organization of educational work to increase the level of pedagogical and psychological literacy among the population through their distribution;

- "Is your child ready for school?" On local television. It is necessary to conduct a series of demonstrations with the participation of experts on the subject. The expected results of the implementation of the proposals are as follows: - Development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 will help ensure the implementation of the tasks set out in the Concept;

- The quality of preparation for school education of children aged 5-7 not covered by preschool education will increase;

- The level of pedagogical and psychological literacy of the population will increase; - The spiritual environment in families is healthy;

- Effective preparation of the child for school education in the family promotes the transition of the child from the crisis of the transition from play to educational activities without socio-psychological and physical harm;

- serves as a basis for the full upbringing, education and development of the child's personality in the process of primary school education.

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РАСПРОСТРАНЕНИЕ ЧИСЛЕННЫХ МЕТОДОВ ИНТЕГРИРОВАНИЯ**Хамзаев Иномжон**¹ **к.т.н., доц., Ферганский Политехнический Институт****Махаматжонов Жавлонбек Сирожидин угли**² **Группа М2-20 «ИОК» магистрант, Ферганский Политехнический Институт**

Весьма распространенным элементом тонкостенных конструкций, широко используемых в авиации, судостроении, ракетной технике и других областях машиностроения, являются пластинки прямоугольной формы, ослабленные одним либо несколькими отверстиями или вырезами. В зависимости от формы и размеров последних в механике выделилось несколько самостоятельных путей исследования. Одно из направлений, большинство инженерных задач приходится решать приближенными методами. К особенно популярным относятся метод конечных разностей (МКР), метод конечных элементов (МКЭ). Эти методы по существу идентичны, сводят решение континуальной задачи к решению систем алгебраических уравнений.

*Следует подчеркнуть, что метод конечных разностей (МКР) стал популярным задолго до появления ЭВМ, однако современная вычислительная техника стала несомненно важнейшим стимулятором дальнейшего развития и широкого приложения сеточных методов к решению самых задач, выдвигаемых инженерной практикой.

Опыт показывает, что с помощью МКР на современных ЭВМ средней мощности можно решать более сложные задачи.

*Применение конечных разностей заменяют производные отношениями конечных величин, вместо одного дифференциального уравнения решают систему линейных алгебраических уравнений.

Известно, что после того, как сформулирована та или иная задача механики деформируемых сред, становятся необходимым отыскать решение исходных дифференциальных уравнений при заданных граничных условиях. С усложнением задач аналитическое решение не всегда оказывается возможным, в этих случаях обращаются к какому-нибудь численному приближенному методу. С 40-х годов используется метод сеток [1-3].

Этот метод стал особенно широко распространяться с появлением быстродействующих вычислительных машин, эффективно решать сложные задачи и автоматизировать все этапы вычислений.

Особенность метода исследования, основанного на конечных

разностях, состоит в том, что дифференциальное уравнение изгиба, а также граничные условия при использовании такого метода, согласно требованиям, удовлетворяются в узлах наносимой сетки. Этого достаточно, если рассматриваются простейшие деформируемые системы, например, сплошная упругая изотропная пластинка. Однако, когда рассматриваемая пластинка имеет прямоугольные вырезы, для удовлетворения граничным условиям на его внутреннем контуре требуется вводить гораздо больше число узлов сетки в сравнении с остальной частью деформируемой системы. Это приводит к появлению громоздкой системы алгебраических уравнений, следовательно, и усложняет дальнейшее развитие задачи.

Необходимо помнить, что решение на основе методом конечных разностей всегда остается приближенным. Степень точности зависит от густоты нанесенной сетки. Существенная особенность метода конечных разностей связана со сходимостью решения при густоты сетки, когда требуется достичь определённой точности: Иногда в отличие от общепринятых уравнений метод сеток в котором неизвестными считаются значения исследуемой функции в узлах сетки, за неизвестные принимают, кроме значений самой функции, ещё и значение ее первых производных. В этом случае точность удовлетворения граничным условиям оказывается менее зависимой от густоты сетки. При решении задачи в такой постановке появляется возможность более полного (а не в отдельных узлах) удовлетворения граничным условиям на внутреннем и наружном контурах.

Замена рассматриваемой пластинки сеточной областью соответствует задаче аппроксимации реальной системы к сетке приводит в теоретическом анализе к системе линейных алгебраических уравнений относительно неизвестных дискретных значений изучаемой функции. Структура уравнений зависит от характеристики сетки.

Для пластинок и оболочек с отверстиями решение плоской задачи теории упругости связано со значительными математическими трудностями, поэтому в большинстве опубликованных работ, посвященных устойчивости подобных конструкций, докритическое напряженное состояние чаще всего аппроксимируется приближенными формулами, а иногда считается равномерным. Такой подход к исследованию позволяет провести хотя бы качественное выявление влияния геометрических размеров, условий опирания и мест расположения отверстий на значение критических параметров, а в некоторых случаях получить и достаточно точные их величины.

Известные исследования о пластинах с прямоугольными отверстиями

посвящены определению их плоского или изгибного напряженного состояния. Ставя перед собой цель развить и применить метод сеток к решению задач устойчивости прямоугольных пластин, получено более точные результаты благодаря увеличению густоты сетки и применению приближенных выражений функций, представленных рядами Тейлора в окрестности кромок рассматриваемой пластины, для внеконкурсных точек. При исследовании критических напряжений пластин предполагается, что вплоть до момента потери устойчивости напряжения в пластине не превосходят предела упругости. Распределение напряжений в пластине не с отверстием во всех точках до потери устойчивости считается однородным. Это упрощающее предположение эквивалентно наложению дополнительной связи, устраняющей в докритическом состоянии влияние отверстия. Такую связь можно осуществить, заполнив отверстие веществом, полностью воспринимающим напряжение плоского деформированного состояния, но не влияющего на деформации изгиба.

Наложение новой связи, как известно, повышает критические значения нагрузок, так что приведённые в статье результаты позволяют указать те значения нагрузок, при которых пластинка с отверстием заведомо потеряет устойчивость. Конечно, нагрузками мы называем лишь активные силовые воздействия. Реакции дополнительной связи входят в решение неявно, через напряжения плоского деформированного состояния.

При определении критических значений сил, приложенных в срединной плоскости пластинки, при которых плоская форма равновесия становится неустойчивой и пластинка начинает выпучиваться, в этом случае пользуется методом конечных разностей в безразмерной форме. Обобщенное в общем виде для любого узла сетки, можно всегда представить как систему n обыкновенных тринадцати членных разностных уравнений, составленных для всех n внутренних узлов сетки, нанесенной на пластинки.

Анализ многочисленных работ подтверждает, что метод конечных разностей имеет ряд преимуществ перед другими методами:

- а). возможность решения задач практически с любыми граничными условиями (частичная заделка, точечное опирание, вырезы ит.д.);
- б). простота используемого математического аппарата;
- в). однообразие вычислений упрощает программирование для вычислительной машины, так как для много операция можно использовать стандартные программы;

При отсутствии программной записи управлений или матриц коэффициентов рекомендуется применять шаблоны.

Следует отметить и недостатки метода:

1) значительная погрешность результатов решений, достигающая в некоторых случаях 10-15 % при обычно принимаемой схеме сетки. Для получения удовлетворительного приближения часто требуется наложение на исследуемую область густой сетки и решение системы уравнений с большим числом неизвестных;

2) громоздкость вычислительных работ по составлению и решению детерминантных или матричных уравнений высокого порядка;

3) отсутствие всякой общности решения, т.е. аналитического выражения искомой функции. Приходится вычислять массу частных ее значений, даже если в этом нет необходимости;

4) даже при небольшом изменении сторон, нагрузок и граничных условий задачи весь процесс составления и решения необходимо произвести заново.

Этих трудностей можно избежать, если уравнение взять в безразмерной форме, т.е. ввести в уравнение отношение стронно и отношение интенсивности нагрузок, и для нахождения характеристического значения параметра применять метод итерации при помощи ЭЦВМ.

Распространение численных методов интегрирования в последние годы обусловлено, с одной стороны, тем, что современные технические проблемы обычно приводят к сложным дифференциальным уравнениям, которые редко удается проинтегрировать в замкнутом виде, с другой стороны, доступностью вычислительных машин.

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Annotatsiya. Fan, texnika va texnologiyalar taraqqiyotining bugungi darajasi bilan bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning kasbiy tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish jarayoni orasidagi mavjud nomuvofiqlikni bartaraf etish zarurati oliy ta'lim tizimida zamonaviy pedagogik va axborot texnologiyalarining yetarli joriy etilmaganligi sababli yanada yuqori dolzarblik kasb etmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar. Axborot, fundamental tushunchalar, masofaviy ta'li, «Kadrlar tayyorlash Milliy dasturi», intellectual, an'anaviy, dasturiy ta'minot, texnik xarakteristika.

O'zbekiston Respublikasining «Kadrlar tayyorlash Milliy dasturi»da oliy ta'lim tizimi oldiga qator muhim vazifalar qo'yilgan. Jumladan, mustaqil bilim olishni individuallashtirish, masofaviy ta'lim tizimi texnologiyasini, uning vositalarini

ishlab chiqish va o'zlashtirish, yangi pedagogik hamda axborot texnologiyalari, tayyorgarlikning modul tizimidan foydalangan holda talabalarni o'qitishni jadallashtirish ana shunday dolzarb vazifalar sirasiga kiradi. Fan va texnikaning mavjud yangiliklari ularni o'quv dasturlari va darsliklari mazmuniga jadal kiritishni talab etadi va bu orqali talabalarning zamonaviy bilimlarini shakllantirishga zamin yaratadi. Zamonaviy o'qitish texnologiyalarining joriy etilishi va turli metodik yondashuvlar esa, o'z navbatida, talabalarda ko'plab fundamental tushunchalarni nisbatan yengil va mustahkam

shakllanishiga qulay sharoit yaratadi.

Ma'lumki, fan va texnika jadal sur'atlar bilan rivojlanayotgan bugungi kunda ko'plab ilmiy bilimlar, tushuncha, tasavvurlar va axborotlar hajmi keskin ortib bormoqda. Bu bir tomondan fan va texnikaning yangi bo'limlari va sohalarining shakllanishini ta'minlayotgan bo'lsa, ikkinchi tomondan, fanlar orasida hukmron bo'lgan chegaralarni buzib, integratsiya jarayonini jadallashtirishni talab etadi.

Ta'lim yo'nalishlari «boshidan kechirayotgan» bunday differentsiyalashish jarayonining o'qitishda o'z aksini yetarli darajada topa olmayotgani ham bugungi oliy ta'lim tizimida ma'lum muammolarni keltirib chiqarmoqda. Xususan, ta'lim mazmuni va to'plangan boy ilmiy axborotlarning unda aks etishi orasida uzilish vujudga kelmoqda. Shu sababdan o'qitishni va o'quv materiallarini bayon etishni takomillashtirish tamoyillarini qayta qarab chiqish zarur. Bunday muammolarni bartaraf etishda ta'lim jarayoniga zamonaviy pedagogik va axborot

texnologiyalarini joriy etish va ulardan foydalanish maqsadga muvofiqdir. Zamonaviy ta'lim tizimi shaxsga yo'naltirilgan xarakterga ega bo'lishi, ya'ni shaxsning har xil xususiyati va sifatiga e'tibor qilgan holda differentsiyalangan bo'lishi zarur. Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan o'qitish avvalo ta'limning paradigmasini o'zgartiradi. Shu paytga qadar mavjud ta'lim tizimida o'qitish ustuvor sanalgan bo'lsa, ayni paytda jamiyatning axborotlashuvi davrida ustuvorlik - o'qishga o'rgatishga yo'naltirilgan. Shu sababdan ta'limning o'qituvchi-darslik-talaba paradigmasi talaba-darslik o'qituvchi paradigmasi bilan o'rin almashishi zarurdir. Zamonaviy pedagog kadrlar yangi statusga ega bo'lib, uning vazifasi eng avvalo

talabalarning mustaqil bilim olish faoliyatini tashkil etishga, bilimlarni mustaqil egallashga va ularni amaliyotda qo'llash malakalarini shakllantirishga qaratilmog'i lozim. Ushbu maqsadlarni amalga oshirish jarayonida o'qituvchi o'qitishning metodlari, texnologiyalarini shunday tanlashi kerakki, ular talabalarga tayyor bilimlarni o'zlashtirishigagina yordam berib qolmasdan, ayni paytda, ularda bilimlarni turli manbalardan mustaqil ravishda o'zlashtirish, shaxsiy nuqtai nazarning shakllanishi, uni asoslashi, erishilgan bilimlardan yangi bilimlar topishda foydalanish malakalariga ega bo'lishlariga ham vosita bo'lishi lozim. Bunday o'qitishni rivojlanuvchi ham deyish mumkin. Shakl va mazmunning rang-barangligi talabaning qiziqishi, imkoniyati va shaxsiy xususiyatidan kelib chiqib, taklif etilayotgan hollardan tanlash imkoniyatini beradi. Bunday imkoniyat ta'lim

tizimida ham o'z aksini topishi zarur. Ko'p sathli o'qitish mazkur muammoning yechimi bo'la oladi deyish mumkin. Hozirga paytdagi o'quv mashg'ulotlarining tashkil etilishi talabadan kundalik fanlar majmuasi bilan ham, ular bo'yicha beriladigan topshiriqlar majmuasi bilan hisoblashishni talab qiladi. Bu esa amalda ko'plab muammolarni keltirib chiqaradi.

O'qitish nazariyasida yangi pedagogik va axborot texnologiyalarini bir-biridan ajratish mumkin emas, chunki yangi pedagogik texnologiyalarning keng joriy etilishi ta'lim paradigmasini o'zgartiradi va faqat zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalarinigina yangi pedagogik texnologiyalarning imkoniyatlaridan samarali foydalanishni ta'minlaydi. Ta'lim muassasida zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalari muhitini tashkil etish bosqichlari psixologik axborot muhitini yaratishdan boshlanadi. Texnologik va ilmiy natijalar, yaratilgan dasturiy

mahsulotlar asosida zamonaviy vositalar va metodlardan foydalanishga ehtiyoj shakllantiriladi. Bunda har bir ta'lim muassasida individual va maslahat mashg'ulotlar asosida pedagoglarni mustaqil va kompyuter ta'limi tizimini tashkil etish kerak. O'qitish jarayonini kompyuterlashtirish (axborotlashtirish)da ikki yo'nalishni ajratish mumkin: kompyuterni o'quv faoliyatining vositasi sifatida

qo'llashning barcha usullarini o'zlashtirish hamda kompyuterdan o'rganish ob'ekti sifatida foydalanish. Kompyuterni texnik xarakteristikalarining va dasturiy ta'minotining takomillashib borishi, didaktik imkoniyatlarining kengayishi uning

o'qitish vositasi sifatida yangi xossalarini namoyon qilmoqda. Kompyuterlar yordamida o'qitishning rivojlanish tarixida ikki tizim: an'anaviy va intellektual o'qitishni ajratish mumkin.

Intellektual o'qitish tizimining asosiy xususiyati shundaki, u o'quv masalalarini hal etishda barcha bosqichlar xususiyatlarini inobatga olgan holda o'quv faoliyatini boshqarishni nazarda tutadi. Intellektual o'qitish tizimida individuallashtirilgan o'qitish o'quvchining dinamik modeli asosida amalga oshiriladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati.

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ФОРМА ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ И ПРОВЕДЕНИЯ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАНЯТИЙ ПО ПЛАВАНИЮ

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Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются форма организации и проведения учебных занятий по плаванию и организация обучения для тех, кто не умеющих плавать и создание условий для безопасности проведения занятий на воде и разные упражнения в воде и постепенное овладение техникой спортивного и прикладного плавания.

Ключевые слова: бассейн, плавание, водоём, санэпидстанция, инструктор по плаванию, дыхание, кровообращение

Abstract: The article discusses the form of organizing and conducting training sessions in swimming and the organization of training for those who cannot swim and the creation of conditions for the safety of training on the water and various exercises in the water and the gradual mastery of the technique of sports and applied swimming.

Keywords: pool, swimming, reservoir, sanitary and epidemiological station, swimming instructor, breathing, blood circulation

Введение

В настоящее время существуют различные формы обучения и организации уроков плавания. Процесс организации и проведения занятий по плаванию связан с определенными мероприятиями: проверка и подготовка места занятий; обеспечение требований безопасности занимающихся; подготовка обучаемых к занятиям плаванием; подготовка преподавателя к проведению занятий. Проверка и подготовка места для занятий заключается в том, что перед началом занятия преподаватель обязан осмотреть ванну бассейна и проверить наличие оборудования и инвентаря, нужного для занятий.

Материалы и методы исследования.

Основная форма организации и проведения учебных занятий по плаванию - групповой урок. Он делится на три части: подготовительную, основную и заключительную. Первая часть урока - подготовка и организация занимающихся, объяснение нового учебного материала, упражнения на суше: легкая пробежка в течение 1-2 мин, разогревающие упражнения типа утренней зарядки, подготовительные упражнения, имитирующие движения пловца. Основная часть урока - упражнения в воде и постепенное овладение техникой спортивного и прикладного плавания. Заключительная часть урока предусматривает: снижение физической нагрузки, проведение игр и купания. Помимо учебных занятий основного урока обучение плаванию можно начинать с утренней гимнастики с включением упражнений, имитирующих движения пловца. Обучение плаванию можно проводить индивидуально, с каждым ребенком в отдельности.

Приемы обучения:

1. Ребенок под наблюдением взрослого опускается с головой под воду, садится на корточки и делает выдох в воду.

2. садится на корточки под водой и, задержав дыхание.

3. ложится на спину, вытягивает руки, слегка разводя ноги.

Для занятий в воде необходимо подготовить два купальных костюма, шапочку, махровое полотенце.

Лодки, катера и все малые суда, принадлежащие спортивным лагерям, детским базам отдыха, должны быть зарегистрированы в установленном порядке в городских и районных советах. Общества спасания на водах и ежегодно перед началом сезона представляться на технический осмотр.

Все лодки и другие малые суда должны храниться в местах, специально отведенных для этой цели, и находиться под замком. Лодки и другие малые суда перед отплытием проверяются на исправность и оснащаются спасательными средствами. Приказом по лагерю (базе) должны быть назначены лица, ответственные за хранение, техническое состояние и эксплуатацию судов. Прежде чем допустить детей к прогулке на лодке, следует провести занятие по изучению правил безопасности.

Каждый должен знать, что:

сидеть в лодку следует осторожно, ступая посередине настила;

нельзя пересаживаться в лодке с места на место во время ее движения, садиться на борт лодки, раскачивать лодку, нырять с нее;

Категорически запрещается переходить из одной лодки в другую во время катания. Необходимо объяснить детям, что нарушение этих правил

может привести к тому, что лодка опрокинется.

Следует научить детей, как действовать в случае несчастья если лодка перевернулась, главное - не растеряться. Перевернутая лодка хорошо держится на воде и может служить спасательным средством. Оказавшиеся в воде должны сохранять спокойствие и до прибытия помощи держаться за лодку и толкать ее к берегу, опав под плот, баржу или парус опрокинувшейся лодки, ни в коем случае нельзя закрывать глаза. Открыв глаза, следует плыть в том направлении, откуда виден свет. Это значит, что поверхность воды близко. Тот, кто умеет плавать, в первую очередь оказывает помощь не умеющему держаться на воде.

Спасать вплавь следует одного тонущего, затем другого; невозможно одновременно спасать вплавь нескольких человек.

При катании детей необходимо присутствие взрослого в каждой лодке. Он должен уметь управлять судном, хорошо плавать, знать приемы оказания неотложной помощи пострадавшим на воде .

Категорически запрещается:

- а) Нагружать лодки и другие малые суда сверх установленных норм ;
- б) пересекать курс идущих судов;
- в) подходить близко к проходящим судам;
- г) кататься вблизи пристаней и причалов;
- д) проводить прогулки детей на лодке, отдаляясь от берега более чем на 100 метров;
- е) катание детей на самодельных лодках , катерах , плотах и т . д
- ж) катание при неблагоприятных метеорологических условиях.

Результаты и обсуждения

Несчастные случаи на лодках нередки при нарушениях правил эксплуатации плавсредств: плохом техническом состоянии, слабой подготовке водителей, перегрузке лодки. Гребная лодка во всех случаях должна уступать дорогу моторным и парусным судам. Нельзя выходить на фарватер . Услышав частые и короткие сигналы судов . гребная лодка должна отойти от проходящего транспорта на безопасное расстояние . Во время хода волну следует резать носом лодки . Повороты на высоких волнах делать не следует .

Тонущему, может быть оказана помощь с катера или шлюпки с использованием спасательных средств .

Причины гибели людей на воде условно можно разделить на три группы:

1. ослабление организма, вызванное хроническим заболеванием

(эпилепсией, пороком сердца), ухудшением общего состояния после перенесенного заболевания и т.д.

2. Перегрузка организма (бывает даже у хороших пловцов от переохлаждения, чрезмерных мышечных усилий, перегревания, психологической неподготовленности и т.п.)

3. Неожиданная травма (от удара волны, удара головой о твердый или режущий предмет), попадание в водоворот, в илистый грунт, в глубокое место, в сильную струю течения, в заросли водных растений и т. д.

Причиной переохлаждения в воде может быть, в зависимости от обстоятельств: низкая температура воды длительное пребывание в воде и недостаточная тренированность пловца.

При медленном охлаждении вначале - усиливается частота дыхания, учащается работа сердца, увеличивается кровяное давление и скорость кровотока, появляется озноб. Повышается возбудимость нервной системы. Внешний признак переохлаждения -- «гусиная кожа» (сокращение капиллярных мышц). Затем в зависимости от индивидуальных особенностей организма начинается мелкая становится бледно-какая дрожь всего тела и зевота, кожа синюшной, а движения - скованными. Пульс в это время прощупывается с трудом и становится реже на ударов, часты позывы на мочеиспускание.

Низкая температура воды вызывает ряд моментальных заболеваний. Холодная вода может при попадании в наружный слуховой проход вызывает раздражение вестибулярного аппарата, которое может проявляться тошнотой, потерей ориентировки, головокружением, бледностью. В таком состоянии даже умеющий плавать постепенно опускается под воду.

Заключение

Подводя итоги, еще раз хотелось бы отметить, что при обучении плаванию решаются следующие основные задачи:

— укрепление здоровья, закаливание организма человека, привитие стойких гигиенических навыков;

— изучение техники плавания и овладение жизненно необходимым навыком плавания;

— всестороннее физическое развитие и совершенствование таких физических качеств, как сила, гибкость, выносливость, быстрота, ловкость;

— ознакомление с правилами безопасности на воде.

Обучение плаванию является частью физического воспитания детей и направлено на комплексное решение задач физического воспитания

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